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Effects of Mastery-Learning-Approach on Performance and Retention in Islamic Studies Concept among Public Primary School Pupils in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the “Effects of Mastery-Learning-Approach on performance and retention in Islamic Studies Concept among Public Primary School Pupils in Katsina State, “The study was guided by two objectives, questions and hypotheses. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design which included a pre-test, post-test and post-test. The study population included all 66,831 (31,735 boys and 35,096 girls) grade 5 pupils from 469 public primary schools in six (6) local government areas under the Katsina Zone Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) State Universal Basic Education (SUBEB). The study sample consisted of 90 grade 5 primary school pupils purposively drawn from two intact classrooms in two sample schools. The instrument used to collect data was the Islamic Studies Performance Test (ISPT) and the Islamic Studies Retention Test (ISRT). The ISPT was validated by the experts and pilot tested, and the internal consistency reliability was 0.85. Two research questions were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses tested using an independent sample t-test at a significance level of 0.05. The results showed that primary school students who learned Islamic studies using the mastery learning approach (MLA) performed significantly better than those who learned the same content using the conventional method. From the results of the study it was discovered that mastery-learning-approach help in enhancing students’ academic performance and retention in Islamic studies concept among public primary school pupils. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that education stakeholders and curriculum planners (in Islamic studies curriculum document) should place a emphasis on the adoption of the mastery learning approach in the teaching and learning process.

Keyword: Islamic studies, mastery-learning-approach, conventional method, academic performance, retention.

Introduction

Mastery Learning Approach (MLA) is an education approach based on the concept that all learners can learn when provided with conditions suitable to their situation. Adam and Marshall (2022) asserted that Mastery learning approach is closely connected to competency-based learning as an observable behaviour of the students to incorporate and exhibit knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes and can proceed to learning other content with complexity at their own phase (Adam, & Marshall, 2022). Hence, being competent in a particular subject area describes the student to have acquired the necessary skills in all the three learning domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) in a certain context at a defined stage of education or practice (FME, 2018).

According to Filgona, & Sababa (2017) Bloom expounded that when learners are typically distributed on aptitude and each student received quality instruction, sufficient learning time required to accomplish the task then most students are expected to achieve mastery standard. Hence, there would be slight or no significant relationship between student’s aptitude and achievement. Subsequently, Filgona & Sababa (2017) viewed Mastery Learning Approach as one of instructional strategies whereby students are given unlimited opportunities to master a particular unit of lesson after assessment typically 70% - 100%, before moving to the next unit. Mastery learning approach provide more time for students to repeat the learning activities in Islamic studies. In the words of Olorumaiye (2024) grade of “A1” represents excellent academic accomplishment that corresponds to an percentage ranging from 75% - 100%, indicating that the learner has adequate mastery of subject matter as maintained in biological and physical sciences, legal system, engineering and technology disciplines.

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Furthermore, researchers on the effectiveness of mastery learning approach such as Ejodamen and Iserameiya (2018) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of mastery learning approach on Students' Academic Achievement by Gender in Basic Technology (BTE) in Edo State, Nigeria. Quasi-Experimental design was adopted involving experimental and control groups. They found that that female students taught BTE with MLA performed relatively higher in their post-test academic achievement than the male students. However, the findings revealed that both male and female taught with MLA performed significantly higher in there post-test academic achievement in BTE than those taught with Direct Instruction Strategy (DIS). Similarly, Animola and Bello (2019) conducted a study, which determined the comparative effectiveness of Mastery and Peer-to-Peer Learning Strategies in Improving Junior Secondary Students' learning outcomes in Basic Science in Owo Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The researchers found that PLS and MLA showed effectiveness in improving the students' attitude to Basic Science with PLS as the most effective. The study concluded that the PLS produce significantly better academic performance and retention of Basic Science concepts by students than MLA.

Accordingly, Adeniji, Ameen, Dambatta and Orilonise (2018) conducted a study, which examined the effect of mastery learning on senior secondary school students' achievement and retention in circle geometry in Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria. They discovered that senior school students' academic achievement in Geometry improved significantly when taught using Mastery learning approach. Even though, the researchers found non-existence of differences in gender and in the achievement of low, medium and high scoring students when taught with Mastery learning approach. Moreover, there was a significance difference in the post test mean score and retention score of students taught circle geometry using Mastery learning approach as compared to their pre-test scores. In addition, Tukur (2018) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of mastery learning approach in enhancing the students' academic achievement in mathematics in Gombe metropolis of Gombe State, Nigeria. Tukur found that students who were exposed to mastery learning had enriched academic achievement in mathematics. Eventually, results on the posttest mean scores of the students revealed that there is a significant effect on the academic achievement of the experimental group in which the MLA had been introduced. Hence concluded that students exposed to MLA performed better than students who were taught in the traditional teaching method. Moreover, results exemplify that there is a significant relationship between the students' attitudes toward mathematics and their academic achievement in mathematics.

Consequently, Hussain and Suleiman (2016) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Bloom's Mastery learning approach on 9th grade students' academic achievement and retention in English language in Khurram Karak, Pakistan. The researchers discovered that the Bloom's Mastery learning approach, positively influences students' academic achievement and retention in English language concepts as compared to traditional learning approach at secondary school level. In addition, Ali, Jabeen and Lubna (2017) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Mastery learning approach (MLA) on learning retention of secondary school students in Mathematics, in Mardan district of Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa in Pakistan. Donald (2019) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Mastery learning approach on senior secondary school students' interest, achievement, and retention in genetics in education Zone C, Benue State, Nigeria. Findings revealed that students taught using MLA performed significantly higher mean achievement scores in genetics than their counterparts been taught using conventional learning approach. Findings indicated that significant difference exist in the learning retention of students in experimental group. Conversely, Uzezi (2020) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Mastery Learning Instructional Strategy (MLIS) on secondary school students' achievement and retention of Chemistry concepts in Jalingo Educational Zone in Taraba State, Nigeria. Uzezi's result contradicts the result of present study and other reviewed works as it revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of high, moderate and low ability students regarding MLIS; there was also no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in chemistry.

Academic performance simply refers to the extent students achieved the educational outcomes in school subjects and extra-curricular activities provided to influence desirable behavioural changes to fit into the society they belonged (Tukura, et al 2020). In other words, academic performance entails the extent a student accomplished the educational objectives assessed through evaluation to predict the students' potentialities in learning experiences been exposed to within a specified period of time (Tukura, et al 2020). Latter Grades (A = 70 -100, B = 60 – 69, C = 50 – 59, D = 40 49 and F = 0 – 39) are assigned to represent the students' aptitude levels on both cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning domains (Tukura, et al 2020). Consequently, the retention ability according to Durojaiye et al. (2021) is the learner's ability to retain experiences at a later time". While Tukura, et al. (2020) stated that, the ability to store and remember ideas and facts is termed as retention. It also means the extent to which a student has achieved the educational goals.

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Islamic studies is one of teaching subjects taught at basic, post basic, tertiary and university education levels in Nigeria aimed at inculcating the sound moral values among children for wellbeing and patriotism. FME (2018) stated that “the title ‘Islamic Studies’ is chosen in preference to all previous titles such as Islamic Religious Knowledge (IRK), Islamic Religious Studies (IRS) and The Religion and National Values (RNV) since it is more comprehensive and therefore fitting the subject matter in the curriculum.” FME (2018) defined Islamic Studies as the totality of learning experiences centered on the relationship between man and his Creator and between man, his fellow men and other creatures. On the other hand, Dauda (2018) viewed Islamic Studies as a teaching subject that comprehensively encompasses all the temporal and spiritual spheres of human life from the most insignificant to the most-fundamental sectors for prosperity.

Furthermore, Islamic Studies is one of school subjects that requires thorough understanding of all its contents for application in daily living. Therefore, education in the Islamic viewpoint produces a cultured, well-behaved, considerate, reasonable and God-fearing individual (FME, 2018). Learners have varying learning abilities, styles and the pace at which they learn contents, which differs from their counterparts. In line with this, the FME (2018) empathized the use of modern teaching techniques such as demonstration, questions and answers, guided discovery, simulation, story-telling, brains storming, cooperative learning, inquiry, field trips, and concept mapping, which have been studied and found to be effective to varying degrees, in improving pupils’ academic performance and retention of learned concepts.

According to FME (2018) Islamic studies represents complete aspects of Islam for it primarily focus on four sources of Shariah; Qur’an and Prophetic Traditions (Hadith) as primary sources and Consensus of Scholars Views (Ijma’) and Analogical Deductions (Qiyas) as secondary sources. These sources further falls naturally into various interconnected subdivisions been incorporated in the new primary and post primary 9-Year Basic Education Curriculum that includes; the Arabic Alphabets, Qur’an, Tajwid, Hadith, Fiqh, Sirah and Tahdhib, which in turn requires mastery. The fore, pupils must attain certain level of mastery for Arabic Alphabets to enable them write and read Arabic letters, words, verses and short chapters of the Qur’anic texts correctly with precision and moderate speed. Also, pupils must have mastery of Qur’anic recitation with rules of Tajweed to avoid unnecessary errors while reading occasionally or in daily prayers (Salat).

Consequently, reciting the Qur’ān or memorizing its chapters is in itself not enough to attain mastery except when accompanied by reflection and practical application in daily life. However, companions of the Prophet Muhammad (Peace be upon him) demonstrate certain level of mastery in Qur’anic recitation through formative and summative assessment before they progress to learning the next chapter or verses as contained in Suratul Baqara “*O ye who believe! Do not say ambiguous words [to Allah’s Messenger] but say words of respect, and listen....*” (Qur’an 2:104). Also the Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon him) teaches his companions through demonstration technique tenets of all steps involved in performing worship acts (Ibadat) so as attain certain mastery level before progressing to higher levels. This will enable them to extend the knowledge to other companions whom were absent during the instruction. In a hadith reported by ‘Abdullāh ibn ‘Amr ibn al-‘ās (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that the Prophet (may Allah’s peace and blessings be upon him) said: “*Convey from me even if it is one verse, and narrate from the Children of Israel, and there is no sin in that. And whoever intentionally tells a lie against me, let him assume his seat in Hellfire.*” Sahih/Authentic Hadith (Related by al-Bukhari: 3461). The Qur’an 2:104 stated above depicts that the Companions of the Messenger of Allah (may Allah’s peace and blessings be upon him) while taking Qur’an lessons request for enough time to enable them memorize with full understanding (mastery) before proceeding to subsequent content. Moreover, the Messenger of Allah (may Allah’s peace and blessings be upon him) command to convey to people the knowledge inherited from him of the Qur’an and the Sunnah on condition that the conveyer is knowledgeable of what he conveys and comprehends it. The conveyance of these messages requires sound memory retention capacity and mastery to avoid unnecessary errors and falsehood attribution to Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Mastery of Prophetic traditions (Hadith) concerning sayings, actions and tacit approval is compulsory upon Muslims in order to negate the fabricated Ahadith. Fiqh which covers all aspect of religious practices or worship (testimonies, salat, sawm, zakat and hajj) with understanding. Sirah portrays the collection of Islamic historical events of Prophets/Messenger of Allah and their nations, righteous servants and wrongdoers. Tahdhib explains Islamic mannerism of peaceful coexistence with creatures on the universe. The Messenger of Allah, Prophet Muhammad (SAW) usually send some of his famous companions (Aliyu ibn Abi Talib, Mu’az ibn Jabal, Abdullahi ibn Mas’ud: may Allah be pleased with them all) who mastered the knowledge or skills on concepts related legal and juristic matters, business transactions, *Tauhid* (Monotheism), *Salat* (Five Daily Prayers), *Zakat* (Alms giving), and *Hajj* (Pilgrimage) to other towns and cities outside Madina as instructors. Moreover, the entire curriculum requires teachers to use a participatory and exploratory teaching methods much more inspiring, motivating, interesting and effective toward prompting the positive attitude and understanding of the pupils for optimal growth and development (FME, 2018).

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According to Busari (2018) pupils mastery in Islamic Studies still not yielding positive result because of some critical factors such as teachers lack of skills to harness the explicit instructional objectives with the lesson, Islamic studies teachers not well versed in Arabic language, persistent use of inappropriate teacher-centred instructional methods, students' learning styles, shortage of school facilities, learners problem with Arabic as second language learning, learners persistent difficulties to contrast between the articulation of (/ ا / ع / ح / ه / د / ض / ط / ت / ث / س / ص / ذ / ز / ظ /) Arabic voiced and voiceless sounds at the initial and final positions, educational policy among others (FME, 2018). The researcher discovered from existing literature that numerous studies have been conducted on the effects of mastery learning approach on students' achievement in English language, Mathematics, Physical, Biological, Technological and Social Sciences at secondary school and tertiary education levels in different localities. To this end, this study was carried out to provide empirical evidence on the effects of mastery learning approach to gather with learning retention on Primary School pupils' academic performance and retention of concepts in Islamic studies in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA).

Statement of the Research Problem:

The Islamic Studies curriculum has been designed to inculcate balance mental and moral values among primary school pupils at a formative stage. According to FME (2018) successful implementation Islamic Studies curriculum largely depends on teachers' capability to use appropriate innovative learner-centered instructional strategies, and selection of relevant teaching aids (real and improvised). A 5 years statistics indicated declining pupils' academic performance in Islamic Studies internal examination results of 10 public primary schools, under Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA), ranging from 2019 - 2023 academic sessions, see appendix 2 showing the statistics.

The statistical summary of pupils' academic performance in the Islamic studies internal examination results obtained from 10 public primary schools in Jibia LGA of Katsina State ranges from 2019 - 2023 academic sessions. Record of 2019/2020 academic session out of 4426 primary 6 pupils only 1404 representing 32.9% have achieved a bench mark mastery level of 70% - 90%. Also, in 2020/2021 session out of 3666 only 1035 pupils with 28.5% achieved mastery level. Meanwhile, in 2021/2022 the academic performance record of 3144 only session 1100 of 34.3% reached mastery standard. Likewise, in 2022/2023 the pupils' academic performance record depicts that out of 2861 only 841 of 33.7% achieves mastery standard.

Furthermore, the academic performance record of 2023/2024 indicated that out of 3617 only 977 pupils with 29.2% accomplishes mastery standard. It is shocking that the academic performance and retention ability of primary school pupils in the internal examination results of Islamic studies out of the grand total of 17,714 primary 6 pupils only 5357 with 31.7% obtained distinction or achieved mastery standard of 80% -90%. These result points to the fact that the pupils' academic performance and retention ability is below the mastery level of the expected minimum standard of 70% - 100%. Thus, the learners persistent poor academic performance could be attributed to lack of retention of the subject matter as most Islamic Studies teachers uses the conventional teaching method 'chalk and talk' which is boring and uninspiring. Therefore, this study intends to investigate if this leaning model can be applicable for teaching Islamic studies subject to enhance academic performance and retention skills among the public primary schools pupils in Katsina state.

Objectives of the study:

1. To examine the difference in the mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method.
2. To assess the difference in the mean retention of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method.

Research Questions:

1. What is the difference between the mean academic performance score of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method?
2. What is the difference between the mean retention rate of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance Score of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean retention rate of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method.

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Methodology

The research design was quasi-experimental comprising a pre-test, a post-test and a post-test. The study was a field experiment with one independent and conditional variable being teaching technique and the two dependent variables were academic performance and retention levels of the students. The study population consisted of 66,831 (31,735 males and 35,096 females) Grade 5 pupils from 469 public primary schools in six (6) local government areas under the Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) of Katsina State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB). The study sample consisted of 90 Grade 5 pupils purposively drawn from two intact classrooms in two sample schools. School A with a class of 44 pupils was assigned to experimental group (EG) and in school B the other class with 46 pupils was assigned to control group (CG) respectively. The instrument used for data collection was the Islamic Studies Performance Test (ISPT) and the Islamic Studies Retention Test (ISRT). The ISAPT was validated by three experts and pilot tested, and the internal consistency reliability was 0.85. The experimental group received instruction using Islamic studies concepts using a mastery learning approach while the control group received instruction using a conventional teaching method. Furthermore, the treatment for both groups lasted for six weeks. Two research questions were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test at a significance level of 0.05 as a criterion for acceptance or rejection.

Results

Mean and standard deviation statistical data analysis was used to answer the research question 1 in table as shown below:

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method?

Mean and standard deviation statistical data analysis was used to answer the research question 1 in table 1 as shown below:

Table 1: Summary of the post-test mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving)

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	Experimental	24.09	3.05	Accepted
2.	Control	20.91	3.09	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows that the difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students who learned the meaning of Zakat (charity) using the mastery learning approach (M = 24.09, SD = 3.05) and those who learned the same concepts using the conventional teaching method. (M = 20.91, SD = 3.09) is 3.18 in favor of the mastery learning approach group. This shows that the experimental group performed better than the control group in terms of students' academic achievement in Islamic studies.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method?.

Mean and standard deviation statistical data analysis was used to answer the research question 2 in table 2 as shown below:

Table 2: Summary of the post-test mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving)

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	Experimental	24.09	3.05	Accepted
2.	Control	20.91	3.09	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

From Table 2, it could be seen the difference between the mean retention scores of the students taught the Zakat (Alms giving) using mastery learning approach (M = 26.05, SD = 2.00) and those taught same concepts using the conventional

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teaching method ($M = 22.65$, $SD = 4.30$) is 3.39 in favour of the mastery learning approach group. This indicates that the experimental group gained more than the control group in terms of the students' retention ability in Islamic Studies.

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Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method.

Independent sample t-test was used in testing the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05, in the table 3 as shown below:

Table 3: t-test Summary on the difference between the mean academic performances of primary school pupils

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
		24.09	3.05	
		20.91	3.09	Sig.

**Significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance*

Table 3 shows that the difference in academic achievement between students who learned the meaning of zakat (alms) using the mastery learning approach (M = 24.09, SD = 3.05) and those who learned the same concepts using the conventional teaching method (M = 20.91, SD = 3.09) was statistically significant (t = 4.911, df = 88; p = 0.000), at a significance level of 0.05. This implies that the experimental group performed significantly better than the control group. Thus, there is a significant difference between the two groups, as confirmed by the high value of the effect size.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean retention of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method.

Independent sample t-test was used in testing the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05, in the table 4 as shown below:

Table 4: t-test Summary on the difference between the mean retention of primary school pupils

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
		26.05	2.00	
		22.65	4.30	Sig.

**Significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance*

Table 4 shows that the difference between the retention ability of students who learned the meaning of Zakat (almsgiving) using the mastery learning approach (M = 26.05, SD = 2.00) and those who learned the same concepts with the conventional teaching method (M = 22.65, SD = 4.30) was statistically significant (t = 4.833, df = 88; p = 0.000), at a significant level of 0.05. This implies that the experimental group performed significantly better than the control group. Thus, there is a significant difference between the two groups, as confirmed by the high value of the effect size.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the results of this study is based on the research questions answered and the hypotheses tested. Therefore, the results of the first research question and the first hypothesis show that there is a significant difference between the average performance of primary school students assigned to the experimental and control groups who were taught the concept of the importance of Zakat (charity) using the approach of mastery learning significantly higher with p value = 0.000 \leq alpha value of 0.05 and those who are taught using the lecture method. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. This result confirmed Ejodamen and Iserameiya (2018) who found that there was a significant difference in the average academic performance of students taught in basic science and technology using the mastery learning approach and those taught with the lecture method. However, this result does not agree with Animola and Bello (2019) who found that there was no significant difference in the average academic performance of student teachers in basic science and technology using 'a peer learning strategy and who achieved significantly better results than those who were taught the same content using the mastery learning approach

The results of the second research question and the second research hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference between the mean retention of primary school students assigned to the experimental and control groups who were taught the concept of the importance of Zakat (giving alms) using mastery learning. The approach was significantly higher with a p value = 0.000 \leq alpha of 0.05 and its counterpart learned the same material using the mastery learning course. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. However, this finding is consistent with the findings of

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Adeniji, Ameen, Dambatta, and Orilonise (2018), Tukur (2018), and Nchelem (2020) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean retention of students after they had learned mathematics concepts using the mastery learning approach and those taught using the lecture method. Similarly, this is consistent with Uzezi (2020) who found a significant difference in retention skills between students taught chemistry concepts using the mastery learning approach and the lecture method. However, these results are not in agreement with those of Animola and Bello (2019) who found that peer work improved students' retention skills in basic science and technology. However, in the mastery learning approach, learning objectives are broken down into simpler units so that each group has 70-90% mastery of them. In addition, students are provided with learning opportunities to retain the concepts learned. Remedial opportunities are provided to ensure that all students master a unit before moving on to the next.

Conclusion

From the results of the study it was discovered that mastery-learning-approach help in enhancing students' academic performance and retention in Islamic studies concept among public primary school pupils.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The government should make it mandatory to use the mastery teaching approach, primarily to learn and teach Islamic studies concepts to facilitate academic achievement.
2. Islamic studies teachers should be trained on how to engage elementary school students to facilitate retention.

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